

Conference Abstract

Designing an International Critical Zone Network of Networks

Jeffrey S Munroe[‡], Elizabeth Boyer[§], Bhavna Arora[|]

[‡] Middlebury College, Middlebury, United States of America

[§] Pennsylvania State University, State College, United States of America

[|] Lawrence Berkeley Lab, Berkeley, United States of America

Corresponding author: Jeffrey S Munroe (jmunroe@middlebury.edu)

Received: 21 Apr 2025 | Published: 28 May 2025

Citation: Munroe J, Boyer E, Arora B (2025) Designing an International Critical Zone Network of Networks.

ARPHA Conference Abstracts 8: e156530. <https://doi.org/10.3897/aca.8.e156530>

Abstract

The “*Designing an International Critical Zone Network of Networks*” workshop will bring together scientists, network coordinators, and stakeholders to explore strategies for fostering global collaboration in Critical Zone (CZ) science. The workshop is planned as part of the CZ-NoN (Critical Zone Network of Networks) project supported by the US National Science Foundation AccelNet program. A key focus of CZ-NoN is strengthening collaboration across existing research networks, including LTER, CZOs, and other long-term environmental observatories, by identifying pathways for greater connectivity, coordination, and knowledge exchange. Participants in this workshop will reflect on experiences with CZ research, discuss institutional and disciplinary barriers to integration, and outline strategies for building a cohesive global CZ research community. The workshop will also address observatory design, exploring how long-term monitoring efforts and standardized core data collection can enhance scientific understanding of CZ processes, inform sustainable management practices, and address pressing environmental challenges. Through sharing of lessons learned from past experience, and cataloging of collective goals for the future, workshop participants will contribute to the creation of a foundation of ideas for use in guiding how existing CZ research entities could be integrated to form a cohesive international scientific community.

Keywords

Critical Zone, Network of Networks, global, international

Presenting author

Jeffrey S. Munroe

Presented at

WORKSHOP

Funding program

AccelNet

Grant title

AccelNet Design: Accelerating Critical Zone Science with an International Network of Networks

Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.